

CREATIVE POTENTIAL OF A PERSON AND FEATURES OF ITS DEVELOPMENT IN SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract. *This article focuses on the creative potential of a person and the features of its development in schoolchildren. In addition, aspects related to the creative potential of the individual will be considered in developing the creative abilities of schoolchildren.*

Keywords: *personality, individual's creative potential, creativity, student, creative ability, concentration of personal potential.*

Increasing the social and economic value of every person's life is the main task of today. In this case, the interests of society, family and the state coincide. Ensuring the freedom of quality education, healthy lifestyle and effective employment for pedagogy is related to the formation of the personality of the pupil and the study of the level features of his motivational and demanding field, creative possibilities (personal potential).

A person - as defined by psychologists - is a person included in the system of such psychological characteristics that are socially conditioned, manifested in social relations and processes, stable and determine the moral behavior of the person himself and those around him..

The concept includes only the individual and personal characteristics of a person, their combination that distinguishes a person from other people. Personal development occurs as a result of socialization and upbringing of a person. A child who has natural anatomical and physiological conditions for the formation of a personality, in the process of socialization, learns the achievements of humanity and interacts with the world. The abilities and functions formed in this process reproduce the human qualities that have been historically formed in the individual. A child's assimilation of reality is carried out with the help of adults in his activities, therefore, the educational process is the leader in the development of a person. Based on what the child has already learned, adults organize his activities to master new aspects of reality, new forms and characteristics of behavior.

Taking into account the above, it is necessary to pay attention to the development of personal potential of students in school years. As an example, it is possible to pay attention to the development of pupils' creative abilities in the course of the lesson. Because the development of creativity is also important in the development of personal potential.

It is recommended to make effective use of the leading technologies, methods and tools, innovative projects of today's modern education field in order to develop creativity in pupils studying in general education schools. With this, the opportunity to improve the personal potential of the pupils will expand even more. Because they are brought up to be creative thinkers, able to turn the situation to their side with their creative ability in any situation.

Solving many problems requires a significant increase in human strength, therefore, when describing a person, it is important to determine what part of his mental and physical potential he can direct to solving personal tasks. This situation can be called the concentration of personal potential. This indicator of personal potential is closely related to willpower and creativity.

The development of a person is carried out in activities controlled by the system of motives specific to this person. In the most general form, the development of a person can be expressed as a process of a person's entry into a new social environment and integration into it as a result of this process. When a person enters a relatively stable social community, under favorable conditions, he goes through three stages of personal development: adaptation, integration, socialization. The relationship between a person and the outside world is becoming more complicated, and this leads to the formation of personal potential. Personal potential is formed in every person throughout his life, and the most important life stage is adolescence.

Personal potential is a higher level of the hierarchy of mental control of human behavior, it is actually an individual structure of mental potential.

Human potential is realized primarily in the external objective environment, in social relations, in the social world. Criteria of the effectiveness of the influence of the environment on the formation of personal potential, researchers distinguish the implementation of ideological, professional, production and educational functions of the environment.

As can be seen from the above, first of all, development of pupils' creativity and creative abilities will serve to increase their personal potential in the future. Or it causes them to awaken an internal motivation to improve their personal potential already during the school period. This serves to increase the desire of pupils to develop their creativity.

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